

'COMPOSITE MATERIALS APPLIED TO THE DESIGN OF FAIL-SAFE DEVICES'

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Summary

This paper explores the possibilities afforded by the application of composite materials to fail-safe devices and outlines the design approaches involved.

Introduction

For general design work, design engineers are usually prepared to 'make do' with available materials. From a strength/deformation point of view, any variation in material properties and any doubt regarding the in-service loading of a component can be countered by the use of a safety-factor. However, in the field of safety-devices the concept of a design safety-factor is untenable because much more control over failure loads and deformation characteristics is required. For example, in the case of safety-rupture diaphragms, which are employed in industry to protect pressure vessels and so on from catastrophic failure, it is essential to be able to forecast the bursting pressure of the diaphragm to within, say, $\pm 5\%$. In such a specialized design application a sound knowledge of material properties is more important than in the area of general engineering design.

Each type of fail-safe arrangement has its own peculiar design advantages and drawbacks. The mode and efficiency of operation of a safety device depends on the design of the assembly, the method of assembly and also on the deformation and/or fracture characteristics of the material employed. A

design approach could be to decide on the operating characteristics most desirable and then to produce material having the appropriate load-extension curve. To this end, a study of composite materials, such as self-adjusting interface composites, which often have special properties that can add an extra dimension to the design of fail-safe devices, could well prove advantageous.

Composites with non-fracturing reinforcing elements

Morley and Millman (1) have shown it possible to produce fibre reinforced composite materials in which fibres are arranged not to fracture during overstrain conditions. This is achieved by a stress controlled reversible decoupling mechanism operating at the fibre matrix interface. As an applied tensile load is increased, decoupling starts to occur at the centre of a long fibre because the stresses carried by the fibre are at a maximum in these regions. The degree of decoupling increases in magnitude and extends outwards towards the ends of the fibres as the stress is increased. Eventually a sufficient length of interface is decoupled to permit the reinforcing element to be drawn through the composite structure. If the tensile load is reduced the bonding between the reinforcing element and the rest of the composite structure is restored. By use of this mechanism, new types of load-deformation relationships can be obtained for fibre reinforced composite systems.

Reinforcing elements of this type, so far studied, have consisted of steel hypodermic tubes containing a helical core of steel wire. The helix angle is very large (approximately 85°) and the diameter of the helix when unstressed is greater than that of the internal diameter of the tube. A frictional force resisting the displacement of the wire within the tube is generated along the line of contact and this diminishes as the tensile load carried by the helical core increases. By a suitable choice of geometry, fracture of the core wire can be prevented by tensile stresses transferred to it from the tube by frictional shear stress transfer across the core/tube interface. The tensile stress carried by the core rises from zero at the free ends and on the central regions approaches some upper limiting value σ_{\max} asymptotically.

The two-part reinforcing elements can be used to reinforce a sheet metal structure by attaching the tubes directly to the sheet. Within the elastic range of the material the core and sheath reinforce the metal plate in the conventional way. Individual sheath elements can be arranged to fail at a particular strain value by the presence of flaws or weak points and the average effective limiting reinforcing strength of the tubular

reinforcing phase can be controlled by the number, distribution and severity of such flaws. In this way sheath elements can be caused to fracture into a number of short lengths having a very much reduced reinforcing ability compared with the initial continuous lengths. The reinforcing ability of the core elements is however unimpaired since this part of the reinforcing phase does not fracture. If the flaws carried by the sheath elements are particularly severe it can be arranged for the reinforcing ability of this phase to be lost before the core elements debonding stress. In this case the core elements carry an increasing stress, up to their limiting debonding stress σ_{\max} , as the deformation of the composite structure continues. This is occurring by an increasing elastic extension of the core elements. Eventually, when the core element limiting debonding stress is reached, further deformation causes the cores to be pulled through the tubular sections against frictional losses at an almost constant stress level. During this stage of deformation the metal plate may be work-hardening so that the deformation stress for the total structure can be increasing.

Fail-safe devices

The load-extension curves for the composite material described in the previous section are based on uniaxial tension. One of their important features is that a large extension at uniform or decreasing load can be achieved which may result in the dissipation of a great deal of dynamic energy in a controlled manner. To illustrate the possible utilization of this feature a number of safety-devices are considered.

Safety-rupture diaphragms

In the design of single-layer safety-rupture diaphragms, an example of which is depicted in Figure 1, the parameters influencing the bursting pressure of a metal disk are (a) disk material properties, (b) disk shape, (c) disk dimensions in the plane of the diaphragm and (d) disk thickness (2).

The simplest way of achieving different diaphragm bursting pressures is to change the initial disk thickness. Unfortunately, because of metal sheet supply and stocking problems, the manufacturers of rupture diaphragms do not always have the full flexibility of this particular design parameter. To overcome these difficulties designers often use two sheets of the same metal or sheets of different metal in combination. In the latter case the bursting pressure of the combination is predicted simply by adding the bursting pressure of one disk to the bursting pressure of the other. Beese and Peters (3) have

shown that this empirical approach, whilst not being theoretically correct, is sufficiently accurate for all practical purposes, especially when natural variation in material properties is taken into account.

Beese and Peters suggested that the use of an unbonded laminate as a rupture diaphragm could have other advantages when used to protect pressure systems where the fluid is a liquid. For single layer disks made of conventional material, such as killed steel or soft brass the stress-strain curves for which are shown in Figure 2, the graph of pressure against dome height is usually of positive slope to the point of rupture. In the case of an unbonded laminate, if the less ductile material is placed on the pressure side, there is the possibility of two-stage rupture with unrestricted bulging of the more ductile sheet after the inner disk has failed. (See Figure 3). For cases where a pressure vessel contains a liquid which is being maintained at very low or zero flow rates, the additional small volume, which corresponds to the difference between the bulged disks heights, may however allow a pressure drop following the rupture of the inner disk. The lower pressure may be sustained by the outer disk without rupturing. Unfortunately, the difference in the dome heights at the two fracture points are usually fairly small and the expansion in volume achieved may be too low a percentage of the total volume of the pressure system to be effective in reducing the pressure to a safe level without the rupture of the second, more ductile disk. A greater volume expansion after the maximum pressure point has been reached may be possible if a material system with different stress-strain characteristics to those depicted in Figure 2 is used for the diaphragm.

The stress-strain curves for three different material systems are shown in Figure 4. Curve 1 shows the stress-strain characteristics of a material which would produce an increase in dome height at constant pressure. Curve 2 is a more realistic stress-strain curve; a diaphragm manufactured from such a material system would have a pressure-dome height curve which had a substantial portion occurring at constant pressure. A diaphragm manufactured from material depicted by curve 3 would experience a maximum pressure at a relatively small dome height followed by a large expansion of the dome under decreasing pressure conditions. (See Figure 5).

Some control over the load deformation characteristics of a reinforced disk can be obtained through progressive fracture of the more brittle reinforcement, to reduce the load carrying ability, coupled with the increase in load carry ability through the strain-hardening of the ductile metal disk. However, the failure strain limit is now set by the fracture of the inner,

ductile metal disk.

So far the non-fracturing reinforcing elements have been considered to be distributed uniformly over the metal sheet and probably arranged in a parallel fashion. An alternative approach is however possible in which radial straps are used to reinforce the plate with stress controlled decoupling devices attached to their extremities. In the simplest form these devices could consist of corrugated strips clamped between flat parallel metal plates. (The basic principle of such devices has been examined elsewhere (1)). The corrugated strip can be withdrawn from between the plates when the critical debonding stress is reached. The corrugations can be arranged, if desired, to protrude beyond the ends of the parallel plates and virtually any desired load/extension relationship can be obtained from a suitable choice of geometry. By this means the end loads carried by the reinforcing straps can be made to change in any desired fashion with increasing deflection of the rupture disk, energy being absorbed by frictional losses in the process.

Figure 6 shows a schematic arrangement for a rupture diaphragm assembly that could possess the attractive pressure-dome height characteristics shown in Figure 5 if a suitable selection of materials is made. The cut-out sections depicted in the plan view are to allow the radial drawing-in of the concentric corrugations to take place. Traditionally rupture diaphragms are supplied in the partially domed condition. If no hysteresis is experienced on unloading the proposed assembly from a pressurized dome height greater than that required to achieve the maximum pressure, fail-safe pressures could be predicted with great accuracy. This added advantage would be applicable to both liquid and gaseous systems.

Containment of pressure vessels

When a pressure system fails the result is less dramatic if pressurized liquid is concerned than if pressurized gas is the working fluid (See Figures 7 and 8). The explosive potential of pressurized gas systems is well known; the possible extent of any catastrophic failure is governed by the rate at which the escaping gas does work which is equal to the product (volume flow rate) (difference in pressure). If a system could be devised to absorb some of the work done and possibly to decrease the rate of volume flow, a certain degree of protection would result when other safety devices, such as pressure relief valves, had failed to operate or had proved to be inadequate. A cylindrical pressure vessel could be contained by wrapping it with sheets of metal linked together by self-adjusting elements as depicted in Figure 9.

Automobile safety

Throughout the world concern has been expressed about the safety of motor-cars and their occupants. Some action has also been taken; safety belts, collapsible steering wheels and the like are, more or less, common features in many modern cars. Self adjusting interface composites could well have applications in this field. Millman and Chappell (4) have discussed several applications.

Criticism has often been levelled at safety-belts because they frequently arrest the user too drastically during impact. A more gradual deceleration could be achieved if a self adjusting link were introduced into the design. Preliminary studies have been made of these devices as energy absorbing links attached to one end of a motor vehicle seat belt (4). They have been found to operate predictably and reliably in such applications.

Car bumpers are usually rigid although some hydraulic systems are in use which cut down the intensity of impact. Another modification is to coat the entire bumper with a thick layer of rubber. An alternative design is shown in schematic form in Figure 10.

Many serious injuries are caused to driver and passengers by side collision. The doors and body work give some protection but they collapse rather too readily with insufficient absorption of impact energy. If the inside of the doors were lined with a self-adjusting interface layer much greater amounts of energy could be absorbed. This type of lining could also be applied to the front apron; to add extra energy absorbing powers the grill could also be modified. To add further to the protection of the driver and front seat passenger, especially with transverse engine cars, the bulkhead could be lined in order to cut down the possibility of leg-crushing.

Conclusions

In this paper attention has been drawn to the possible use of stress controlled frictional interfaces in the construction of composite materials and devices. The emphasis has been on the ways in which unusual, and useful, load deformation characteristics can be obtained. Other aspects are discussed elsewhere (J.G. Morley. 'Fibre reinforced composites with non-fracturing reinforcing elements'; this conference.) In particular the non-fracturing primary reinforcing phase provides a fail-safe characteristic and also inhibits crack growth in the rest of the composite structure even under fatigue loading conditions. Also the strain diffusing mechanism associated with

controlled interfacial debonding can cause a very large portion of an engineering structure to take part in a deformation and energy absorbing process where, with existing materials, only localized failure would occur as a result of local stress concentrations. This factor is of importance, for example, when the maximum amount of energy is required to be absorbed by localized impact of a large engineering structure.

References

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4. Millman, R.S. and Chappell, M.J., 'Energy absorption by variable shear strength duplex materials' 5th International Technical Conference on Experimental Safety Vehicles, London, June, 1974, 1 - 15.

1. Example of a safety-rupture diaphragm.

2. Typical stress-strain curves for ductile metals.

3. Expansion curves for diaphragms made of ductile metals.

4. Desirable stress-strain curves for diaphragm materials.

5. Non-typical diaphragm expansion curves.

6. Composite safety-rupture diaphragm with circular self-adjusting region.

7. Safety rupture diaphragm burst with air pressure.

8. Safety rupture diaphragm burst with oil pressure.

SELF ADJUSTING
ELEMENTS

9. Cylindrical pressure vessel fitted with self-adjusting safety girdle.

10. Design for car bumper.